

DEDUCTIVE AND INDUCTIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING GRAMMAR

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Abstract: This article contains information about investigation of effectiveness of teaching English by using deductive and inductive approaches of teaching grammar. The investigation also attempts to see which of these two methods has a positive effect on the grammar academic achievement of the secondary school pupils, so it answers to the following questions: What are inductive and deductive approaches of teaching grammar? What advantages and disadvantages they have got?

Key words: Inductive method, Deductive method, elementary level, pre-intermediate level.

Аннотация: В данной статье содержится информация об исследовании эффективности обучения английскому языку с использованием дедуктивного и индуктивного подходов к обучению грамматике. Исследование также пытается увидеть, какой из этих двух методов оказывает положительное влияние на академическую успеваемость учащихся средней школы по грамматике, поэтому оно отвечает на следующие вопросы: что такое индуктивный и дедуктивный подходы к обучению грамматике? Какие преимущества и недостатки у них есть?

Ключевые слова: Индуктивный метод, дедуктивный метод, начальный уровень, средний уровень.

Introduction

Language learning has become important so the question of language teaching by means of different methods and ways attracts the attention of language teachers. Considering most of the educational systems and the needs of English language learners are considered, grammar teaching is seen to be one of the most controversial issues. Therefore, there is a growing demand to examine how the language teachers teach and practice grammar. To teach grammar is very important and it plays a significant role in every English foreign language classroom. And through teaching grammar, teacher aims to enable his students to be able to make progress in their linguistic competence. Learners use grammar as a tool or resource for comprehension, and creation of oral and written discourse efficiently, effectively, and

appropriately depending on the situation . There are two main methods of teaching grammar: deductive method and inductive method. Both deductive and inductive teaching have their advantages and disadvantages and which approach language teachers use can depend on a number of factors, such as the preferences of the teacher and learners, characteristics of language which is going to be learnt, learners’ age. However, perhaps, it is generally accepted that a combination of these two approaches is best suited for the EFL classroom. What is inductive and deductive grammar teaching? What are advantages and disadvantages? Which is better? In this article we will look through some principles of using these approaches.

Deductive teaching is a traditional approach in which information about target language and rules are driven at the beginning of the class and continued with examples. The principles of this approach are generally used in the classes where the main target is to teach grammar structures. For instance, these principles are convenient for the classes that grammar translation method is applied (Nunan, 1991). According to Thornbury’s three basic principles a deductive lesson starts with presentation of the rules by the teacher. Secondly teacher gives examples by highlighting the grammar structures. Then students make practise with the rules and produce their own examples at the end of the lesson (Thornbury, 1999).

Identifies inductive approach as a process where learners discover the grammar rules themselves by examining the examples. In a inductive approach it is also possible to use a context for grammar rules. That is to say, learners explore the grammar rules in a text or an audio rather than isolated sentences. Thornbury (1999) notes that in an inductive approach learners are provided with samples which include the target grammar that they will learn. Then learners work on the examples and try to discover the rules themselves. When students obtain the grammar rules and they practice the language by creating their own examples.

In contrast, they define the inductive researcher as someone who works from the “bottom-up, using the participants’ views to build broader themes and generate a theory interconnecting the themes” (p. 23). And in my opinion the ideas of all mentioned scientists have the same meaning. In deductive method it is believed that teachers should separate themselves from the learners while qualitative teachers are aware that the relationship between them and their students is important in the understanding of the class .Both approaches are commonplace in published materials. Some course books may have practices on one approach or the other as series style, whereas some may be more flexible and have both practices including both approaches according to what is taught. Most inductive learning presented in course books is guided. In other words, exercises and questions guide the learner to work out the grammar rule.

The methods may be different but the goals remain the same and both

approaches have advantages and disadvantages.

The advantages of a deductive approach :

-It gets straight to the point, and so can be time-saving. Many rules especially rules of form can be simply and quickly explained and allow more time for practice and application.

-It gives opportunity for the teacher to deal with language points as they come up, rather than having to prepare some materials in advance.

The disadvantages of a deductive grammar approach:

-Starting the lesson with a grammar presentation may be not understandable for some students, especially at young ages. They may not have sufficient language (language which is used to talk about grammar rules). They may not be able to understand the rules involved.

-Grammar explanation encourages a teacher-centered, transmission-style classroom; teacher explanation is often at higher position than students’ involvement and interaction.

-Such an approach encourages the belief that learning a language is simply a case of knowing the rules.

The advantages of an inductive approach:

- Rules learners discover for themselves (student-centered) how to use, when to use some structures than rules they have been presented with. This makes the rules more meaningful, memorable and acquired.

The disadvantages of an inductive approach:

-Much time and energy are spent while working out rules with students.

-The time taken to work out a rule may be at the expense of time spent in putting the rule to some sort of productive practice.

-It can demand teachers to work on planning a lesson. They need to select and organize the data carefully so as to guide learners to an accurate formulation of the rule, while also ensuring the data is intelligible.

-An inductive approach frustrates students who would prefer simply to be told the rule.

Conclusion

It is necessary for teachers to vary their techniques and ways of teaching according to their pupils’ interests and achievement levels with more emphasis on using the inductive way of teaching grammar. Teachers and instructors are encouraged to participate in different intensive training courses in order to be aware of various modern methods of teaching English language. They also should apply modern ways of teaching in their classes since this is one of the aims of the Ministry of Public Education. Researchers should conduct other studies in order to obtain a more comprehensive idea about which way of teaching is more influential in teaching

grammar. Expected findings of the study indicate that the experimental groups at both primary and university stages are equivalent at the time of starting the experiment and the teaching of English grammar through inductive approach plays a positive role in improving the academic achievement of the students studying English grammar in both levels.

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